

METABOLIC SYNDROME AND COGNITIVE DISORDERS

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KEYWORDS

Metabolic syndrome, cognitive impairment, insulin resistance, inflammation, neurodegeneration, oxidative stress, Alzheimer's disease.

ABSTRACT

Metabolic syndrome (MetS), a cluster of diseases that includes central obesity, hypertension, hyperglycemia, and dyslipidemia, has emerged as a significant public health problem. In addition to its association with cardiovascular disease and diabetes, MetS is increasingly associated with cognitive impairment and neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease. The underlying mechanisms linking MetS to cognitive decline include chronic inflammation, insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and vascular dysfunction, which impair brain health and neuronal function. This article explores the complex relationship between MetS and cognitive impairment, highlights the physiological and biochemical pathways, and discusses preventive and therapeutic strategies to mitigate the impact of MetS on cognitive health. Recognizing the interrelationship between metabolic health and cognitive function is critical for developing integrated approaches to address the dual burden of physical and neurological diseases.

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DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.14507188**

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METABOLIK SINDROM VA KOGNITIV BUZILISH

KALIT SO'ZLAR/
КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА:

Metabolik sindrom, kognitiv buzilish, insulin qarshiligi, yallig'lanish, neyrodegeneratsiya, oksidlovchi stress, Altsgeymer kasalligi.

ANNOTATSIYA/ АННОТАЦИЯ

Metabolik sindrom (MetS), markaziy semizlik, gipertenziya, giperglikemiya va dislipidemiya o'z ichiga olgan kasalliklar klasteri sog'liqni saqlash uchun muhim muammo sifatida paydo bo'ldi. MetS yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari va diabet bilan bog'liqligidan tashqari, kognitiv buzilishlar va Altsgeymer kasalligi kabi neyrodegenerativ kasalliklar bilan tobora ko'proq bog'liq. MetSni kognitiv pasayish bilan bog'laydigan asosiy mexanizmlar surunkali yallig'lanish, insulin qarshiligi, oksidlovchi stress va qon tomir disfunktsiyani o'z ichiga oladi, bu miya salomatligi va neyron funktsiyasini buzadi. Ushbu maqola MetS va kognitiv buzilish o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni o'rganadi, fiziologik va biokimyoviy yo'llarni ta'kidlaydi va MetSning kognitiv salomatlikka ta'sirini yumshatish uchun profilaktika va terapevtik strategiyalarni muhokama qiladi. Metabolik salomatlik va kognitiv funktsiya o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni tan olish jismoniy va nevrologik kasalliklarning ikki tomonlama yukini hal qilish uchun integratsiyalashgan yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqish uchun juda muhimdir.

Metabolik sindrom (MetS) - markaziy semizlik, ko'tarilgan qon bosimi, dislipidemiya va giperglikemiya o'z ichiga olgan metabolik anormalliklarning klasteri bilan tavsiflangan multifaktorial holat. Bu harakatsiz turmush tarzi, noto'g'ri ovqatlanish odatlari va semirishning ortib borayotgan tarqalishi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan global sog'liq muammosi. MetS bilan bog'liq asosiy tashvishlar an'anaviy ravishda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari va 2-toifa diabet atrofida aylangan bo'lsa-da, so'nggi dalillar MetS va kognitiv buzilish o'rtasidagi kuchli bog'liqlikni ko'rsatdi [1].

Kognitiv buzilish engil kognitiv nuqsonlardan Altsgeymer kasalligi (AD) va qon tomir demans kabi og'ir neyrodegenerativ kasalliklargacha o'zgaradi. MetS ni kognitiv pasayish bilan bog'laydigan o'sib borayotgan tadqiqot majmuasi metabolik salomatlik miya faoliyatiga qanday ta'sir qilishini chuqurroq tushunish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi. Ushbu bog'lanishning asosiy mexanizmlari murakkab bo'lib, tizimli yallig'lanish, insulin qarshiligi, oksidlovchi stress va serebrovaskulyar disfunktsiyani o'z ichiga oladi, bularning barchasi neyronlarning salomatligi va kognitiv faoliyatini buzadi [2].

1. Metabolik sindrom haqida tushuncha

MetS tashxisi, agar shaxs Xalqaro diabet federatsiyasi (IDF) tomonidan belgilangan quyidagi mezonlardan uchta yoki undan ko'pini ko'rsatsa:

Markaziy semizlik (ko'pchilik populyatsiyalarda bel atrofi erkaklar uchun >94 sm va ayollar uchun >80 sm).

Ko'tarilgan triglitseridlar (≥ 150 mg / dL).

HDL xolesterinning kamayishi (erkaklarda < 40 mg/dL va ayollarda < 50 mg/dL).

Ko'tarilgan qon bosimi ($\geq 130/85$ mmHg).

Ko'tarilgan ochlik qon glyukoza (≥ 100 mg/dL) [3].

MetS tarqalishi so'nggi o'n yilliklarda keskin oshdi, urbanizatsiya, qarish populyatsiyasi va nosog'lom turmush tarzi uning global tarqalishiga hissa qo'shdi.

2. Kognitiv buzilish: ta'riflar va tasniflar

Kognitiv buzilish xotira, diqqat, til va ijro etuvchi funksiyalar kabi aqliy qobiliyatlarning pasayishini anglatadi. Uni quyidagilarga bo'lish mumkin:

Engil kognitiv buzilish (MCI): Oddiy qarish va demans o'rtasidagi o'tish holati, ko'pincha Altsgeymer kasalligining kashshofi hisoblanadi.

Demans: kunlik hayotga xalaqit beradigan sezilarli kognitiv pasayish bilan tavsiflangan progressiv va zaiflashtiruvchi holat. Altsgeymer kasalligi va qon tomir demans eng keng tarqalgan turlaridir [4].

Kognitiv buzilish va MetS o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik metabolik salomatlikni miya salomatligini belgilovchi omil sifatida ko'rib chiqish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

3. MetS va kognitiv buzilishlarni bog'lovchi patofiziologik mexanizmlar

MetS va kognitiv buzilishlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik bir nechta biologik va fiziologik mexanizmlar orqali amalga oshiriladi:

Insulin qarshiligi va miya funksiyasi

Insulin neyronlarning omon qolishi, sinaptik plastika va xotirada muhim rol o'ynaydi. MetS ning o'ziga xos belgisi bo'lgan insulin qarshiligi miyada glyukoza almashinuvini buzadi, bu energiya tanqisligiga va kognitiv disfunktsiyaga olib keladi [5].

Surunkali yallig'lanish

MetS tizimli yallig'lanish bilan bog'liq bo'lib, IL-6 va TNF-a kabi yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarning yuqori darajalari bilan tavsiflanadi. Ushbu sitokinlar qon-miya to'sig'ini kesib o'tib, kognitiv pasayish va neyrodegeneratsiya bilan bog'liq bo'lgan neyroyallig'lanishni qo'zg'atadi [6].

Oksidativ stress

Reaktiv kislorod turlari (ROS) va antioksidant himoya o'rtasidagi nomutanosiblik natijasida yuzaga keladigan oksidlovchi stress neyron hujayralariga zarar etkazadi va sinaptik uzatishni buzadi. MetS oksidlovchi stressni giperglikemiya, dislipidemiya va mitoxondriyal disfunktsiya orqali kuchaytiradi [7].

Qon tomir disfunktsiyasi

MetSda tez-tez uchraydigan gipertenziya va ateroskleroz miya qon oqimini buzadi, bu esa oq moddaning shikastlanishiga va miya atrofiyasiga olib keladi. Ushbu qon tomir o'zgarishlar qon tomir demans va Altsgeymer kasalligiga yordam beradi [8].

Yog' va gormonal disregulyatsiya

Haddan tashqari yog' to'qimalari miya faoliyatiga ta'sir qiluvchi leptin va adiponektin

kabi adipokinlarni ishlab chiqaradi. MetSdagi tartibga solinmagan adipokin darajalari xotira va ijro etuvchi funktsiyaning buzilishi bilan bog'liq [9].

4. MetS-kognitiv buzilish aloqasining klinik dalillari

Bir nechta epidemiologik va klinik tadqiqotlar MetS va kognitiv pasayish o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi:

Uzunlamasına tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, MetS bo'lgan odamlarda MetS bo'lmaganlarga qaraganda kognitiv buzilish xavfi 20-30% ga yuqori.

Kesma tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, markaziy semizlik va gipertenziya MetS komponentlari orasida kognitiv nuqsonlarning eng kuchli prognozi hisoblanadi [11].

Neyroimaging usullaridan foydalangan holda olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, MetS hipokampus hajmining pasayishi va oq moddaning yaxlitligi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ularning ikkalasi ham xotira va kognitiv funktsiya uchun juda muhimdir [12].

Metabolik sindrom va kognitiv buzilish global sog'liq uchun jiddiy muammolarni keltirib chiqaradigan o'zaro bog'liq holatlardir. MetSni kognitiv pasayish bilan bog'laydigan patofiziologik mexanizmlar miya funktsiyasini saqlab qolish uchun metabolik salomatlikni hal qilish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Hayot tarzini o'zgartirish, farmakologik muolajalar va kognitiv treningni profilaktika strategiyalariga integratsiyalash ushbu shartlarning ikki tomonlama yukini kamaytirishi mumkin.

Tadqiqotlar MetS va kognitiv buzilishlar o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro ta'sirni ochishda davom etar ekan, samarali tadbirlarni ishlab chiqish uchun tibbiyot xodimlari, tadqiqotchilar va siyosatchilarni o'z ichiga olgan multidisipliner yondashuv muhim ahamiyatga ega. Metabolik va kognitiv salomatlikni birinchi o'ringa qo'yish orqali biz sog'lom qarish va hayot sifatini yaxshilash uchun yo'l ochishimiz mumkin.

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